

Comparative Analysis of Regulatory Tools, Methods, and Policy Frameworks: National Bank of Ethiopia vs. Developed and Developing Countries

MEAZA WONDIMU TADESSE

A GradXs Researcher enrolled in PhD Program with LIUTEBM University

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Abstract

This study examines financial regulatory frameworks and central banking practices through a qualitative comparative analysis of the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) and selected benchmark central banks from developed and developing economies, namely the Federal Reserve and the European Central Bank, alongside the Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The study adopts a document-based qualitative research approach, reviewing regulatory directives, policy frameworks, supervisory reports, and international standards covering the period 2019–2024.

The analysis is structured around five key regulatory dimensions: prudential regulation and capital standards, supervisory methods and enforcement, monetary policy tools, foreign exchange and capital account management, and financial inclusion and digital finance policies. The findings indicate that while advanced economy central banks emphasize market-based instruments, sophisticated risk-based supervision, and well-developed macroprudential regimes, African central banks apply more directive and development-oriented regulatory approaches to address structural constraints, financial inclusion gaps, and market imperfections.

The study finds that Ethiopia's regulatory framework has demonstrated progress in strengthening supervision, expanding financial inclusion, and introducing an open and managed foreign exchange market. However, compared to peer regulators, limitations remain in monetary policy transmission, capital market depth, and the use of market-based supervisory tools. Drawing on comparative insights, the study recommends a sequenced and context-sensitive reform approach that deepens risk-based supervision, enhances market-based policy instruments, strengthens prudential oversight, and supports innovation in digital finance while preserving financial stability.

Key words: Comparative Regulation, Central Banking, supervision, Financial Stability

1. Introduction

Financial regulation is not monolithic; rather, it reflects a nation's economic ideology, institutional capacity, and stage of development. Financial regulation refers to the set of laws, rules, supervisory practices, and institutional arrangements designed to ensure the stability, integrity, and efficiency of the financial system (Supervision, Basel Committee on Banking, 2022). It encompasses prudential oversight of financial institutions, consumer protection measures, market conduct rules, and macro prudential policies aimed at safeguarding the broader financial system. Effective financial regulation seeks to prevent systemic risks, promote fair and transparent markets, protect depositors, and support sustainable economic growth (International Monetary Fund., 2019).

In many developing economies, central banks shoulder dual mandate: safeguarding monetary and financial stability while simultaneously promoting financial inclusion and economic

development (World Bank., 2020). Within this landscape, the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) serves as a distinct example of a regulator operating in a state-influenced, transitional financial ecosystem, where policy priorities are shaped by evolving market sophistication, and developmental objectives ((IMF)., 2023)

Compared with regulators in advanced economies such as the U.S. Federal Reserve, the European Central Bank (ECB), and the Bank of England, whose frameworks emphasize market discipline, risk-based supervision, and macro prudential tools (European Central Bank (ECB)., 2021) (Federal Reserve, 2022), the NBE still relies heavily on directive-driven oversight, high reserve requirements, and administrative controls as mechanisms for stability and policy steering. When contrasted with developing peers like Kenya or Nigeria, Ethiopia's regulatory landscape shows both constraints and opportunities. (Central Bank of Kenya (CBK)., 2021). (Central Bank of Nigeria., 2022).

This paper examines how NBE's regulatory tools, supervisory methods, and policy frameworks compare with those of selected developed and developing countries. The goal extends beyond descriptive comparison: it seeks to identify actionable pathways for regulatory evolution that respect Ethiopia's unique context while aligning with international best practices and global standards for financial stability.

2. Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research design, enabling an indepth exploration of the National Bank of Ethiopia's (NBE) regulatory tools, supervisory practices, and policy frameworks in comparison with selected developed and developing countries. The approach emphasizes interpretive and contextual analysis rather than quantitative measurement, allowing for understanding of institutional, structural, and policy differences.

2.1 Document and Policy Review

A comprehensive review of regulatory and policy documents were conducted, including:

- Primary NBE documents: directives, proclamations, and supervision manuals covering 2019–2024
- Benchmark central bank publications from developed countries: Federal Reserve (U.S.) and European Central Bank (ECB). These were selected because they represent advanced financial systems with well-established regulatory frameworks, sophisticated supervisory practices, and extensive experience in risk-based supervision, macro prudential regulation, and monetary policy management.
- Benchmark central bank publications from developing countries: Central Bank of Kenya, South African Reserve Bank, and Central Bank of Nigeria. These were selected as representative of emerging African economies with progressive regulatory reforms, digital finance initiatives, and practical lessons for transitional banking systems like Ethiopia's. Including Nigeria provides an additional perspective from a larger, diversified economy with a complex banking system, allowing for a broader understanding of regulatory approaches in sub-Saharan Africa.
- International standards: Basel I–III
- Diagnostic and analytical reports: IMF and World Bank Financial Sector Assessment Programs (FSAPs) and World Bank financial sector studies

This selection allows for meaningful cross-country comparison while focusing on jurisdictions that offer relevant lessons and best practices applicable to Ethiopia's financial and institutional context.

2.2 Comparative Analytical Framework

A structured qualitative framework was developed to compare regulatory practices across five key dimensions:

1. Prudential regulation and capital standards – including risk-based approaches and capital adequacy frameworks
2. Supervisory methods and enforcement – covering onsite/offsite supervision, directive compliance, and enforcement mechanisms
3. Monetary policy tools and transmission – assessing instruments such as reserve requirements, interest rate management, and open market operations
4. Foreign exchange and capital account management – including exchange rate policy and cross-border capital flow regulation
5. Financial inclusion and digital finance policies – evaluating policies promoting access to banking, digital finance, and fintech regulation

This qualitative framework enables a systematic and comparative analysis, highlighting contextual differences, institutional capacities, and potential areas for regulatory enhancement. By focusing on selected central banks, the study ensures a balance between global best practices and regionally relevant insights for Ethiopia.

3. Literature review

3.1 Empirical review

Empirical studies indicate that the financial regulatory policies of the European Central Bank (ECB) and the Federal Reserve (U.S.) are grounded in sophisticated, risk-based supervisory frameworks designed to enhance the resilience and stability of the banking system. These policies emphasize market discipline, forward-looking stress testing, and macro prudential oversight, ensuring that banks are adequately capitalized under adverse economic scenarios (Claessens S. &, 2022).

Vermeulen, R., Hoeberichts, M., Vasicek, B., & Zigràiova, D. (2020) highlights that the Federal Reserve employs its Comprehensive Capital Analysis and Review (CCAR) to assess banks' capital planning, risk exposure, and capital allocation strategies, enhancing transparency and shaping institutional behavior. This reflects a broader paradigm in developed economies, where supervision is characterized by sophistication, technology integration, and risk sensitivity, prioritizing financial stability, market discipline, and innovation (Vermeulen, 2020). Similarly, the ECB's regulatory policies incorporate harmonized standards across multiple euro-area jurisdictions, promoting consistency in risk management, cross-border supervision, and macro prudential policy coordination. Laeven, L., & Valencia, F. suggest that these regulatory frameworks not only mitigate systemic risks but also enhance the efficiency of supervisory resource allocation, focusing attention on higher-risk institutions and activities (Laeven, L., & Valencia, F., 2019).

Singh, D., & LaBrosse, J. R. (Eds.). (2022) shows that U.S. stress tests, starting from the Supervisory Capital Assessment Program (SCAP) and evolving into CCAR, affect banks' behavior around regulatory events. Stress test disclosure can promote financial stability through improved market discipline, though banks may adjust risk profiles to optimize reported outcomes (Singh, 2022)

Mwangi and Koskei (2021) emphasize the CBK's transition to a risk-based supervision (RBS) framework, which they describe as a strategic move from reactive compliance checks to proactive, forward-looking risk assessment. Their research points to improved early warning signals and a more efficient allocation of supervisory resources as key outcomes. However, they also caution that the effectiveness of RBS is contingent on continuous capacity building and data analytics investment within the CBK itself (Mwangi, 2021).

On monetary policy, Ngugi and Kabubo (2019) analyze the CBK's use of a policy rate corridor system and its communication strategy. They find that while the framework is modern and aligns with international best practices, its transmission to market rates can be weakened by structural factors like government borrowing from the domestic market and the dominant influence of a few large banks on pricing (Ngugi, 2019).

According to Alley et al. (2023), historical banking reforms in Nigeria, particularly those implemented in 2004 and 2009, enhanced prudential performance and stability metrics in the sector, showing that the effects of these reforms continue to shape current regulatory outcomes (Ibrahim Alley, 2023).

Similarly, irjems.org (2024) suggests that monetary policy instruments under the direct control of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) including cash reserve ratios, liquidity requirements, and interest rate tools affect commercial bank performance. The source shows that regulatory parameters such as reserve requirements influence banks' risk profiles and profitability indicators in the postpandemic period, highlighting the close interaction between monetary regulation and prudential outcomes (Dr. Suka L. C Adamgbo, 2024).

In Nigeria, Uchenna and Okey (2019) empirically assessed compliance challenges and reported that regulatory duplication and ambiguity often result in confusion and inefficiencies among financial institutions. Their survey of compliance officers from 15 commercial banks found that overlapping mandates between the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), and other regulatory bodies led to increased operational burden and compliance fatigue (Uchenna, 2019).

The scholarly consensus on Ethiopia's financial regulatory framework highlights a persistent tension between control-oriented stability and market-led innovation (Fantu, 2022). Research indicates that while the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) maintains a legally independent mandate, its functional autonomy is frequently compromised by executive priorities and developmental objectives, leading to policy inconsistencies (Geda, 2020). Supervisory effectiveness is further constrained by gaps in risk-based assessment capabilities and technological infrastructure (Abebe, 2020), even as the stringent foreign exchange regime, while preserving reserves, fosters a large parallel market and economic inefficiencies (Tadesse, 2023).

Comparative analysis positions Ethiopia's model as distinctively state-directed, contrasting with the more enabling frameworks of neighbors like Kenya (Fantu, 2022). This approach has delivered stability but at the cost of financial deepening, efficiency, and inclusive growth. External assessments confirm this diagnosis and recommend modernization (Hailu, 2021). Researchers concur that Ethiopia's path forward requires not abrupt liberalization but a sequenced, capacity-building modernization of its regulatory toolkit. This involves strengthening institutional independence, transitioning to market-based monetary operations, fostering an innovation-friendly digital ecosystem, and adopting risk-sensitive supervision—all while maintaining macroeconomic stability during a period of significant economic transition (.

4. Comparative Analysis of Regulatory Tools, Methods, and Policy Frameworks

This comparative study examines the regulatory frameworks of central banking institutions across differing economic contexts. It systematically analyzes the variations in policy instruments, supervisory methodologies, and institutional approaches that characterize financial governance in both advanced and emerging economies. The analysis highlights how developmental priorities, market structures, and institutional capacities shape distinct regulatory philosophies and operational models. By juxtaposing these diverse systems, the study identifies fundamental principles, emerging trends, and contextual adaptations in

contemporary central banking practice. This examination provides an analytical foundation for understanding regulatory evolution and informs strategic consideration of policy development in dynamic economic environments.

4.1 Prudential Regulation and Capital Standards

Prudential regulation and capital standards are critical for ensuring the safety, soundness, and resilience of banking systems across countries.

Federal Reserve (U.S.) and European Central Bank (ECB): According to the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2022) and the Federal Reserve (2022), developed economies such as the U.S. and Eurozone employ risk-based supervision and Basel III-compliant capital adequacy frameworks, including countercyclical and systemic risk buffers. These regulators conduct regular stress testing, monitor liquidity coverage ratios, and adjust capital requirements dynamically based on systemic risk exposures, ensuring that banks maintain sufficient buffers under adverse economic scenarios (Supervision, Basel Committee on Banking, 2022) (Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve. , 2023).

Central Bank of Kenya (CBK): Kenya has progressively adopted risk-based supervisory frameworks aligned with Basel II/III principles, but the approach remains tiered according to bank size and systemic importance. The CBK emphasizes maintaining capital adequacy ratios, monitoring nonperforming loans, and promoting resilience while supporting financial inclusion and sectoral growth (Tyce, 2020) (Central Bank of Kenya, 2023).

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): CBN implements risk-based supervision and enforces capital adequacy standards in line with Basel II/III principles. It has also initiated recapitalization exercises to strengthen bank resilience, particularly after periods of systemic stress (CBN. , 2022).

National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE): According to IMF (2019), Ethiopia’s prudential framework is largely directive-driven, with high reserve requirements and limits on credit allocation (International Monetary Fund., 2019). While the NBE has begun aligning some practices with Basel standards, supervision remains largely compliance-based rather than risk-sensitive. And Ethiopia currently tring to implement Basel II/III.

Table 1: prudential regulation and capital standard

Aspect	National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE)	Federal Reserve (USA)	European Central Bank (ECB)	Central Bank of Kenya(CBK)	Central Bank of Nigeria(CBN)
Regulatory Approach	Direct control; prescriptive and interventionist.	Risk-based supervision; hybrid principles/rules-based.	Single Supervisory Mechanism (SSM); harmonized EU rules	Evolving risk-based supervision; conservative.	Mixed approach with significant supervisory discretion.
Basel Implementation	Basel I (Core principles). Start II/II implementation since January 2026	Basel III (Full, with US enhancements).	Basel III (Full, via CRD IV/V & CRR)	Phase based implementation of Basel II/III since 2015. Final Basel 3.1 reforms started effective Jan 2025.	Phase based implementation of Basel II/III since 2013. Final Basel 3.1 reforms deadline march 31, 2025. (Implementing, with local adaptations).

Minimum Capital Adequacy Ratio(CAR)	8% (Total capital/RWA).	8% of RWA, 2.5% (CET1), Effective Minimum CAR 10.5%	8% of RWA, 2.5% (CET1), Effective Minimum CAR 10.5%	8% of RWA, 2.5% (CET1), Effective Minimum CAR 10.5%	10% (national), 15% (international), 1.0% (CET1) Effective Minimum CAR 11% (national) 16% (international)
Liquidity Requirements	15% Liquidity Ratio (highly conservative).	LCR (100% min) and 100% NSFR for large banks.	LCR (100% min) and NSFR (EU implementation)	Statutory liquidity ratio. Implementing LCR/NSFR	Liquidity Ratio: 30%. High Cash Reserve Requirement (27.5%)
Supervisory Structure	Centralized, direct oversight.	Dual banking system (Fed/OCC/FDIC). Fed supervises holding companies & state members.	SSM: ECB directly supervises "significant" banks; national authorities supervise others	Centralized. CBK is the primary supervisor.	Centralized. CBN is the primary supervisor for banks.

Source: Respective central bank documents review, 2025

The comparative analysis reveals a clear spectrum of prudential regulation and capital standard implementation, broadly categorized into three groups. At one end, the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) operates a basic and directive model, firmly rooted in Basel I principles. Its approach is characterized by static capital and liquidity ratios, direct credit controls, and a primary focus on using regulation as a tool for macroeconomic management and financial stability through prescriptive rules.

In the middle, the Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) represent transitional and active regulators. Both are in the process of adopting more sophisticated Basel II/III frameworks while actively tailoring them to local contexts. A defining feature is their conservative stance, often maintaining capital adequacy ratios significantly above international Basel minimums.

At the other end of the spectrum, the Federal Reserve (Fed) and European Central Bank (ECB) exemplify advanced and complex systems with fully implemented Basel III frameworks. Their regimes are characterized by sophisticated, risk-sensitive models, mandatory and comprehensive stress testing (e.g., CCAR, EU-wide tests), and a multi-layered system of capital buffers (e.g., conservation, countercyclical, and systemic buffers). Supervision is intensive, particularly for globally systemic banks (GSIBs in the US, Significant Institutions in the EU), with a strong emphasis on market discipline and resilience within deep, complex financial markets.

4.2 Supervisory methods and enforcement

Supervisory methods and enforcement mechanisms are essential for ensuring compliance, mitigating systemic risk, and promoting financial stability.

Federal Reserve (U.S.) and European Central Bank (ECB): According to the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2022) and Federal Reserve (2022), developed economies employ a combination of onsite and offsite supervision with a strong emphasis on proactive risk identification and enforcement. The Federal Reserve conducts regular inspections, stress testing, and comprehensive audits of major banks, while the ECB applies its Single Supervisory Mechanism (SSM) to enforce compliance across significant Eurozone banks. Scholars suggest that these agencies maintain high transparency and accountability, which strengthens

supervisory credibility and systemic resilience (ECB, 2023) (Board of governance of federal reserve system , 2022) (Supervision, Basel Committee on Banking, 2022).

Central Bank of Kenya (CBK): CBK uses tiered supervision, combining onsite inspections with offsite reporting and monitoring. Ngugi and Kabubo (2019) shows that Kenya’s enforcement mechanisms include sanctions, corrective directives, and a regulatory sandbox for innovative financial services (Ngugi, 2019). Mwangi and Koskei (2021) show that CBK balances supervisory rigor with flexibility to support innovation while ensuring that banks meet prudential requirements, particularly in areas such as capital adequacy and non-performing loans (Mwangi, 2021).

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): CBN implements both onsite and offsite supervision, focusing on compliance with directives, risk-based reporting, and corrective interventions. According to Adeosun (2021), the CBN employs sanctions, penalties, and targeted inspections to ensure enforcement of prudential and operational standards. The literature suggests that while CBN supervision is robust, resource constraints and complex bank structures occasionally limit its depth and consistency (Sanusi, 2022)

National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE): Ethiopia’s supervisory framework is primarily directive-driven, emphasizing compliance with central directives rather than risk-based assessments. Supervisory methods are largely onsite inspections, with limited offsite monitoring or proactive enforcement mechanisms.

The NBE employs a predominantly onsite and offsite, compliance-based supervisory model, with a strong emphasis on verifying adherence to its extensive and prescriptive directives. Supervision focuses heavily on ensuring banks meet statutory requirements for capital adequacy, liquidity ratios, and priority sector lending quotas (Abebe, 2020). The NBE utilizes directive enforcement and periodic inspections as its primary tools, with interventions often taking the form of formal directives or restructuring orders for non-compliant institutions (Geda, 2020).

Table 2: Supervisory methods and enforcement

Aspect	National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE)	Federal Reserve (USA)	European Central Bank (ECB)	Central Bank of Kenya (CBK)	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)
Primary Supervisory Method	Direct, mix of on-site and off sight inspections & compliance checks. .	Risk-focused, continuous supervision. M ix of on-site exams and off-site monitoring. Data-driven.	Supervisory Review and Evaluation Process (SREP). Joint supervisory teams (JSTs) for significant banks.	Risk-Based Supervision (RBS) framework. Increasing off-site surveillance and targeted on-site exams.	Combination of routine on-site examinations and special investigations. Significant off-site monitoring.
Examination Frequency	Regular but often scheduled; can also be unpredictable.	Continuous for large firms; annual on-site exams for large banks.	Ongoing for significant institutions via JSTs. Full SREP cycle typically annually.	Annual full-scope on-site exams for large banks, more frequent for smaller/weaker banks.	Regular cycle (often annual) for major banks, with frequent special focus exams.

Key Supervisory Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAMELS rating system Prudential requirements On-site verification Credit ceiling directives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAMELS rating system Stress testing (CCAR/DFAS T) Horizontal reviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SREP scoring (1-4 scale) ICAAP/ILA AP review Thematic reviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RBS scoring (Composite Risk Score) Early Warning System (EWS) Peer group analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk-Based Supervision framework Financial Analysis Surveillance System (FASS) Bankers' Committee engagement
Common Enforcement Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monetary fines Suspension of Banking activities like guarantee, FCY related... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Written agreements/Consent orders Civil money penalties (CMPs) Prompt Corrective Action (PCA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capital/liquidity add-ons (P2R) Qualitative measures Fines (via national authorities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial penalties Restriction of business activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heavy financial penalties Removal of senior management Takeover of bank management License revocation
Use of Technology	Low. Relies on manual reporting and physical audits.	Very High. Advanced data analytics, AI for monitoring, and continuous data feeds.	High. Integrated Reporting (IReF) system, centralized databases (AnaCredit).	Growing. Implementing more automated reporting systems and data analytics.	Moderate. Uses electronic submission (FASS) but with room for advanced analytics.

Source: Respective Central Bank document review, 2025

The CBK employs a risk-based supervisory (RBS) framework, integrating both onsite and offsite methods to assess bank risk profiles, governance, and capital adequacy. Supervision is proactive and forward-looking, utilizing technology-driven monitoring systems, stress testing, and regular prudential meetings with bank management. According to Muthiora (2020), the CBK's supervisory effectiveness is enhanced by its collaborative approach with banks, using findings to guide corrective actions rather than purely punitive measures (Muthiora, 2020). The literature highlights that the CBK's supervision is relatively robust and adaptive, though challenges remain in managing the rapid growth of digital credit providers and ensuring consistent oversight across all financial institutions (Mwangi, 2021).

The CBN implements both onsite and offsite supervision, focusing on compliance with directives, risk-based reporting, and corrective interventions. According to Adeosun (2021), the CBN employs sanctions, penalties, and targeted inspections to ensure enforcement of prudential and operational standards. The literature suggests that while CBN supervision is robust, resource constraints and complex bank structures occasionally limit its depth and consistency (Sanusi, 2022).

The Federal Reserve implements a dual supervision system involving both federal and state-level oversight, primarily through a risk-focused framework that emphasizes capital adequacy, liquidity, and operational resilience. Supervision integrates continuous monitoring, stress testing (notably the Comprehensive Capital Analysis and Review CCAR), and regular examinations conducted by Reserve Banks. The literature notes that the Fed's supervision is highly institutionalized and transparent, though its complexity and dual regulatory structure can sometimes create coordination challenges, particularly for large, globally active banks (Hirtle, B., Kovner, A., & Plosser, M., 2019).

The ECB conducts supervision through the Single Supervisory Mechanism (SSM), applying a harmonized, risk-based approach across Eurozone banking institutions. Supervision is structured around the Supervisory Review and Evaluation Process (SREP), which assesses capital, liquidity, governance, and business model sustainability. According to Schoenmaker (2023), the ECB's model is characterized by deep integration with national competent authorities, standardized methodologies, and a strong emphasis on cross-border consistency and macroprudential oversight (Schoenmaker, 2023).

The National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) employs a prescriptive, compliance-focused supervisory model, characterized by its reliance on directive-based oversight and periodic onsite and offsite inspections rather than forward-looking, risk-based analysis. Supervisory activities primarily center on ensuring adherence to its extensive regulatory directives covering capital adequacy, statutory liquidity ratios, and priority sector lending quotas through detailed and often manual examinations. While the NBE holds strong formal enforcement powers, its capacity is constrained by limited technological infrastructure for offsite surveillance, a shortage of specialized supervisory staff, and a focus on verifying rule compliance over assessing underlying institutional risk profiles. This approach contrasts with the more proactive, data-intensive, and risk-sensitive supervisory frameworks employed by central banks in both developed economies and leading developing peers, such as Kenya.

4.3 Monetary Policy Tools

Monetary policy tools are essential instruments used by central banks to influence liquidity, interest rates, credit availability, and overall economic activity. The transmission of these tools into the banking sector and broader economy varies according to institutional capacity, market development, and regulatory frameworks.

Federal Reserve (U.S.) and European Central Bank (ECB): According to the Federal Reserve (2022) and ECB (2021), developed economies rely on market-based monetary instruments such as open market operations, discount rates, reserve requirements, and interest rate corridors. These instruments are complemented by quantitative easing measures and forward guidance to influence liquidity, credit conditions, and economic expectations. (Federal Reserve., 2022) (ECB. , 2021).

Central Bank of Kenya (CBK): CBK uses a hybrid approach combining policy rate adjustments, liquidity ratios, and reserve requirements to influence commercial bank behavior (Mwangi, 2021). The CBK also employs open market operations and moral suasion to manage credit growth and inflation, with transmission effectiveness influenced by the relatively smaller size of financial markets and the prevalence of informal financial channels.

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): CBN employs reserve requirements, liquidity ratios, and interest rate tools as primary instruments for monetary control (Adeosun, 2021) (CBN. , 2022). Additionally, the CBN occasionally issues development-oriented credit directives targeting specific sectors, reflecting its dual mandate of financial stability and economic development.

National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE): According to NBE (2024) and IMF (2019), Ethiopia's monetary policy framework is largely directive-driven, relying on high reserve requirements, liquidity requirement and credit allocation directives. While the NBE is gradually introducing reforms to enhance market orientation, research suggests that the effectiveness of monetary policy transmission remains constrained by shallow financial markets and structural rigidities (World Bank. , 2020).

Table 3: Monetary policy tools

Aspect	National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE)	Federal Reserve (USA)	European Central Bank (ECB)	Central Bank of Kenya (CBK)	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)
Primary Monetary Policy Objective	Price stability & economic development (dual mandate de facto).	Maximum employment & price stability (dual mandate).	Price stability (primary, defined as <2% inflation).	Price stability (primary). Supports economic growth.	Price stability (primary). Supports economic growth & exchange rate stability.
Key Policy Rate	Minimum Deposit Rate (sets floor for savings) & . No single policy rate.	Federal Funds Rate (FFR) target range.	ECB Main Refinancing Operations (MRO) Rate (de facto key rate).	Central Bank Rate (CBR).	Monetary Policy Rate (MPR).
Conventional Tools	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Direct credit controls (sectoral lending quotas). Open Market Operations (OMOs) Reserve Requirement Ratio (RRR). Liquidity ratio 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open Market Operations (OMOs) – primary tool. Interest on Reserve Balances (IORB). Discount Window Lending. Reserve Requirements 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Main Refinancing Operations (MROs). Deposit Facility Rate (floor). Marginal Lending Facility Rate (ceiling). Reserve Requirements 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open Market Operations (Repos/Reverse Repos). Central Bank Rate (CBR) signaling. Reserve Requirements (Cash Reserve Ratio). Kenya Banks' Reference Rate (KBRR) – discontinued but legacy effects. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) signaling. Open Market Operations (OMOs) – mostly T-bills. Cash Reserve Requirement (CRR) – very active tool Liquidity Ratio
Major Obstacles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> high inflation Shallow/absent bond market. Large informal sector. Critical FX shortage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Global financial spillovers affecting domestic conditions. High level of household/debt affecting sensitivity. Balance sheet size complications (QE unwind). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Fragmented banking union (lack of common deposit insurance, capital markets union). One-size-fits-all policy for 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Liquidity volatility from government borrowing. Dollarization of large transactions. High NPLs in some sectors weakening bank balance sheet channel. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Structural fiscal dominance (government borrowing crowds out private sector). FX market illiquidity & multiple

			diverse economies.		practices 3. High inflation expectations anchoring rates high. 4. Large informal sector.
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Source: Respective Central Bank document review, 2025

The framework and effectiveness of monetary policy tools and their transmission reveal a stark divide between advanced and developing central banks. The Federal Reserve and ECB operate in deep, market-based financial systems where price-based instruments (like the policy rate and OMOs) and unconventional tools (QE, forward guidance) transmit effectively through multiple channels (interest rate, credit, asset price). Their primary challenge is managing spillovers and structural heterogeneity within a currency union (ECB). In contrast, the National Bank of Ethiopia relies almost entirely on direct, administrative tools such as credit ceilings, administered interest rates, and forex rationing, resulting in a constrained and directive transmission mechanism with weak market signals.

The Central Bank of Kenya and Central Bank of Nigeria occupy a middle ground, employing a mixed system of market-based and direct tools. The CBK uses a policy rate and OMOs within a fairly transparent framework, with transmission moderated by government borrowing and dollarization. Its management of mobile money liquidity is innovative. The CBN's approach is more interventionist and complex, heavily reliant on aggressive use of the Cash Reserve Requirement (CRR) and frequently adjusting multiple windows to manage liquidity and the exchange rate, often leading to a distorted and less predictable transmission. Across all developing economies, fiscal dominance, shallow financial markets, and external vulnerabilities pose significant obstacles to effective monetary policy transmission that are less prevalent in advanced economies.

4.4 Foreign Exchange Management

Foreign exchange (FX) Policies that govern currency stability, cross-border capital flows, and external financial balance.

Federal Reserve (U.S.) and ECB (EU): According to the Federal Reserve (2022) and ECB (2021), developed economies implement managed floating exchange rates with capital mobility regulations and foreign investment oversight. The Federal Reserve primarily influences the dollar through monetary policy, while the ECB monitors the euro area with cross-border coordination (Board of governance of federal reserve system, 2022) (Supervision, Basel Committee on Banking, 2022).

Central Bank of Kenya (CBK): The CBK adopts a managed float system with FX interventions, an FX auction system, and cross-border capital controls (Central Bank of Kenya (CBK), 2022). Studies indicate that these tools help stabilize the Kenyan shilling and regulate foreign inflows, although market depth and informal channels affect transmission efficiency (Mwangi, 2021).

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): Research shows that the CBN maintains a managed exchange rate while enforcing capital flow regulations, FX repatriation requirements, and licensing of FX transactions (Adeosun, 2021) (CBN, 2022). Scholars suggest that these measures support external stability but can constrain market efficiency and create parallel exchange rate pressures (Sanusi, 2022).

National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE): According to the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE, 2024), Ethiopia introduced an open and managed foreign exchange market framework in 2024, allowing market participation in FX trading while maintaining regulatory oversight. Under this arrangement, exchange rates are increasingly determined through market mechanisms, although the NBE continues to apply foreign exchange controls and prioritization rules to manage scarce FX resources.

Table 4: Foreign exchange and capital account management

Aspect	National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE)	Federal Reserve (USA)	European Central Bank (ECB)	Central Bank of Kenya (CBK)	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)
De Jure Exchange Rate Regime	Managed Floating (since July 2024).	Free floating.	Free floating (Euro).	Floating (with elements of a stabilized arrangement).	Floating (since June 2023 unification).
De Facto Exchange Rate System	Managed float with periodic illiquidity. But the frequent illiquidity causing volatility.	Free floating. Interventions are rare and coordinated (with Treasury).	Free floating for the Eurozone. No routine intervention.	Managed float. CBK actively smoothes volatility via intermittent intervention; operates a wholesale foreign exchange window.	Managed float with periodic illiquidity. but with frequent illiquidity causing volatility. History of multiple windows.
Key Capital Flow Management Tools	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prior approval required for all inward/outward transfers. 2. Foreign exchange rationing (pro-rationing). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoring & reporting of large flows (Treasury). 2. Sanctions regimes (geopolitical tool). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Monitoring of capital flows by ECB & national authorities. 3. No preventive capital controls within Eurozone. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reserve requirements differentiated for local vs. foreign currency deposits. 2. Minimum holding periods for government securities by foreigners. 3. FX position limits for banks. 4. Intervention in spot market. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prohibited list for FX access 2. Quantitative limits on FX purchases for invisible transactions. 3. External debt management (pre-approval by CBN).
Primary Objectives of	1. Exchange rate stability and unified market.	1. Ensure orderly market conditions (ext	1. Ensure price stability (pri	1. Build & maintain reserve buffer	1. Exchange rate stability and unified market.

FX Management	2. Reserve accumulation (often challenged). 3. Control imported inflation. 4. Prevent capital flight.	reme volatility only). 2. Implement international financial sanctions.	mary). 2. Smooth excessive volatility if it threatens price stability.	2. Smooth excessive volatility to anchor expectations. 3. Ensure market liquidity.	2. Reserve accumulation (often challenged). 3. Control imported inflation. 4. Prevent capital flight.
Level of FX Reserves	Critically low	Not a primary policy target.	Not a primary policy target.	Moderate & actively managed.	Moderate but volatile.
Handling of Parallel Market	Officially illegal but large	N/A. No meaningful parallel market.	N/A. No meaningful parallel market within Eurozone.	Small and contained.	Large and systemic historically.

Source: respective central bank document review, 2025

Foreign exchange and capital account management strategies form a spectrum from complete openness to stringent control. The Federal Reserve and ECB represent the fully open, market-determined model. They operate free-floating currencies with fully convertible capital accounts, using FX policy passively to support broader monetary policy goals. Intervention is rare and reserved for addressing disorderly markets.

In stark contrast, the National Bank of Ethiopia operates a highly restrictive, control-based model defined by acute foreign exchange scarcity. Its system is characterized by a heavily managed, multi-tier exchange rate with a large parallel market premium, comprehensive capital controls, and rationing. Policy is geared toward conserving reserves for critical imports, but it creates significant distortions and stifles investment.

The Central Bank of Kenya and Central Bank of Nigeria employ intermediate, managed models but with different emphases. The CBK manages a relatively open capital account with a flexible but smoothed exchange rate, using targeted interventions and macroprudential-like tools (e.g., holding periods) to manage volatile portfolio flows while building reserve buffers. The CBN's approach is more restrictive and interventionist, even after its 2023 market unification. It continues to grapple with managing a controlled capital account, persistent FX illiquidity that fuels a parallel market, and the use of direct administrative measures (like past import bans) to manage balance of payments pressures, reflecting a deeper struggle with external imbalances and policy credibility.

4.5 Financial Inclusion and Digital Finance Policies

Financial inclusion and digital finance policies aim to expand access to banking services and regulate innovations such as fintech and digital payments.

Federal Reserve (U.S.) and ECB (EU): According to ECB (2021) and Federal Reserve (2022), developed economies prioritize broad financial access, consumer protection, and digital payment oversight. Supervisory frameworks cover fintech regulation, cybersecurity, and responsible innovation, with high penetration of digital channels across populations (Supervision, Basel Committee on Banking, 2022).

Central Bank of Kenya (CBK): Kenya has become a global leader in digital finance, with policies promoting mobile money, agent banking, and fintech innovation. Ngugi and Kabubo

(2019) show that CBK employs tiered KYC requirements, regulatory sandboxes, and digital monitoring to support inclusion while safeguarding stability (Ngugi, 2019).

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): Research indicates that CBN gradually regulates digital banking and fintech. Regulatory frameworks focus on payment systems, licensing, and outreach programs, but enforcement and digital adoption remain uneven across regions (Adeosun, 2021).

National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE): According to NBE (2024) and World Bank (2020), Ethiopia's financial inclusion and digital finance policies are nascent, with limited regulatory oversight of fintech and digital banking. Current policies focus on branch expansion, mobile banking pilots, and gradual modernization of financial infrastructure (Gebremichael & Fekadu, 2022).

Table 5: Financial inclusion and digitalization

Dimension	National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE)	Federal Reserve (USA)	European Central Bank (ECB)	Central Bank of Kenya (CBK)	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)
Financial Inclusion Strategy	Government-led developmental approach with mandatory quotas	Market-based with regulatory safeguards focusing on eliminating discrimination	Stability-first integration emphasizing safe, affordable access to basic payment	Innovation-enabled ecosystem model where inclusion is driven by private sector mobile money (M-Pesa)	Target-driven regulatory push with explicit national targets
Digitalization Strategy	Late-stage digital transition with recent liberalization (2023 telco mobile money licensing)	Infrastructure modernization focusing on faster payments (FedNow), cybersecurity, and exploring CBDC,	Pan-European harmonization through PSD2 (Open Banking), digital euro preparation.	Global leader in mobile money integration, with digital finance deeply embedded in monetary policy and daily economic life.	Heavily regulated digital expansion with multiple licensed platforms, a live CBDC (eNaira), and focus on transaction volume growth.
Key Inclusion Metrics (Latest Available)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adult account ownership: ~49% (lowest in comparison) • Digital payments: <20% of adults • Gender gap: Significant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unbanked rate: ~5% of households • Digital banking adoption: ~80% of adults • Disparities: Racial/income gaps persist 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment account access: ~95% of adults • Digital payments: High but varies by region • Cross-border inclusion: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Account ownership: ~80% of adults • Mobile money penetration: >80% of adults • Digital credit: ~40% of adults • Gender gap: Significant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Account ownership: ~64% of adults • Agent network: >1.7 million agents (world's largest) • Digital payment users: Rapidly growing

Regulatory Approach to Innovation	Cautious liberalization after long restriction; recently launched regulatory sandbox; focus on controlling risks in fragile system.	Risk-based, multi-agency oversight with focus on consumer protection, AML/CFT, and systemic risk; "same activity, same risk" principle.	Proportionate regulation balancing innovation and stability; strong focus on data protection (GDPR) and payment service regulation	Proactive enablement with world-first mobile money regulations, regulatory sandbox, and evolving framework for digital credit providers.	Highly prescriptive licensing regime with numerous license categories; active intervention in product design and market operations.
Major Digital Finance Policies	1. Digital Ethiopia 2025 Strategy 2. Licensing of telco-led mobile money (2023) 3. National Payment System Strategy	1. FedNow Service (instant payments, 2023) 2. CBDC research (digital dollar exploration) 3. Fintech innovation offices	1. Digital Euro Project (preparation phase) 2. PSD2/Open Banking implementation 3. Pan-European Payment Initiative	1. National Payments Strategy 2022-2025 2. Digital Credit Providers Regulations (2022) 3. CBDC research group (no plans to issue)	1. eNaira CBDC launch (2021) 2. Payment Service Bank (PSB) licensing 3. Revised National Financial Inclusion Strategy
Unique Characteristics	Digitalization as catch-up strategy in heavily controlled financial system; inclusion driven by agricultural credit mandates rather than digital channels.	Inclusion as fairness objective in already deep financial system; digitalization focused on efficiency, speed, and security rather than basic access.	Cross-border harmonization challenge; digitalization must work across diverse economies with different adoption levels & preference	Digital-native financial system where mobile money preceded widespread banking; digital channels are primary, not alternative.	Scale-driven approach with world's largest agent network; aggressive targets combined with direct central bank intervention in digital finance.

Source: document review, 2025

The Federal Reserve's approach to digitalization and financial inclusion is defined by its risk-based and innovation-supervisory dual mandate. Operating within a mature, complex financial system, its regulatory focus is on systemic stability, cybersecurity, consumer protection, and anti-money laundering compliance rather than foundational inclusion. Key initiatives like FedNow (instant payments) aim to modernize national payment infrastructure, while the rise of neo-banks and fintechs is managed through a combination of federal and state charters and partnership models with licensed banks. Research by Claessens et al. (2018) notes that while digital adoption is widespread, inclusion efforts primarily target the underbanked population, addressing gaps in credit access and transaction fairness rather than mass basic account ownership. The U.S. model demonstrates the challenge of integrating

fintech innovation into a multi-regulator system with a strong emphasis on prudential oversight and legacy bank stability.

The European Union's strategy for digital financial inclusion is anchored in harmonization, open finance, and consumer-centric regulation. The cornerstone policy is the Payment Services Directive 2 (PSD2), which mandates open banking APIs to spur competition and innovation in payments and financial data services. Regulatory priorities include strong data privacy (GDPR), consumer protection, and ensuring a level playing field across member states. The ECB and national competent authorities focus on the systemic implications of fintech growth and the digital transition of incumbent banks. The EU's inclusion strategy is framed around access to affordable payment accounts and leveraging digital tools to enhance cross-border services within the Single Market. As analyzed by Zetzsche et al. (2020), this top-down, standards-driven model has successfully catalyzed a competitive fintech landscape, though implementation and inclusion outcomes vary significantly across member states, reflecting differing national market structures and supervisory capacities.

Kenya has emerged as a global pioneer in digital financial services, underpinned by a progressive regulatory framework. The CBK actively promotes mobile money ecosystems, agent banking, and fintech innovation through tiered KYC requirements, regulatory sandboxes, and real-time digital monitoring systems. This approach has successfully expanded financial inclusion while maintaining systemic stability. Research by Ngugi and Kabubo (2019) underscores that the CBK's enabling stance has been instrumental in fostering widespread digital adoption and positioning Kenya as a benchmark for regulatory innovation in emerging markets.

Nigeria's approach to digital financial regulation is characterized by gradual adaptation, focusing on structured licensing, payment system oversight, and financial inclusion initiatives. While the CBN has established foundational frameworks for digital banking and fintech, research highlights persistent challenges, including uneven regulatory enforcement and regional disparities in digital adoption. Studies such as Adeosun (2021) note that despite progressive policies, implementation gaps and infrastructural constraints continue to limit the depth and consistency of Nigeria's digital finance transformation.

Ethiopia's digital finance landscape remains in its formative stages, with regulatory frameworks primarily focused on expanding physical access through branch networks and mobile banking initiatives. Current policies emphasize gradual modernization of financial infrastructure, with limited dedicated oversight of fintech and digital innovation. According to analyses by Gebremichael and Fekadu (2022) and World Bank assessments, the NBE's cautious and incremental approach has resulted in slower progress in financial inclusion compared to regional leaders, highlighting opportunities for a more assertive and innovation-friendly regulatory evolution.

5. Policy recommendation

To align with international best practices while addressing Ethiopia's unique economic context, the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) requires a comprehensive and sequenced modernization of its regulatory and policy framework. The following recommendations provide a strategic roadmap across all core central banking functions.

1. The National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) should continue transitioning from a predominantly directive-based supervisory model toward a fully risk-based supervisory framework. Drawing on the experiences of the Federal Reserve and the ECB, NBE can strengthen early-warning systems, enhance offsite surveillance, and prioritize supervisory resources toward systemically important and higher-risk institutions. This transition should be phased and capacity-driven to ensure effective implementation. To enhance banking sector resilience, NBE should progressively align capital adequacy requirements with Basel-consistent standards, while

allowing flexibility to reflect domestic market conditions. Lessons from Nigeria's recapitalization efforts and Kenya's tiered capital framework suggest that differentiated capital buffers based on bank size and systemic importance can improve stability without constraining credit growth.

2. Regarding supervisory methods and enforcement, a fundamental shift from compliance-based to risk-based supervision is paramount. This requires investing in a supervisory technology (SupTech) platform to enable integrated data analytics and forward-looking risk dashboards, moving beyond manual, periodic examinations. Enforcement must become more transparent and consistent; establishing a public register of enforcement actions and implementing a formal prompt corrective action framework, with clearly defined triggers for intervention, would enhance deterrence and market discipline. Furthermore, building a dedicated offsite surveillance unit with early warning system capabilities is essential for proactive risk identification.
 3. To strengthen monetary policy tools, the NBE must gradually reduce its reliance on administrative controls. The cornerstone of this reform should be the development of a deep and liquid interbank money market, enabling a shift to a policy rate corridor system as the primary monetary instrument. Phasing out direct lending quotas and replacing them with targeted refinancing facilities would improve credit allocation efficiency. Enhancing transparency through the regular publication of a Monetary Policy Report, complete with inflation forecasts and policy rationale, will guide market expectations and improve the credibility and transmission of monetary decisions. NBE should expand the use of market-based monetary policy tools, including open market operations and interest rate corridors, to improve policy transmission. While administrative instruments remain useful in a transitional economy, experiences from Kenya and Nigeria show that gradual market deepening improves liquidity management and reduces reliance on direct credit controls.
 4. Following the introduction of an open and managed FX market in 2024, NBE should focus on improving transparency, price discovery, and interbank FX trading. Gradual relaxation of FX prioritization rules and enhanced reporting requirements can reduce market distortions while safeguarding external stability. Coordination with fiscal authorities will be essential to manage transition risks. This should be accompanied by a phased roadmap for capital account liberalization, starting with foreign direct investment-related flows, while implementing macroprudential safeguards to manage associated risks. Building external resilience also requires a sovereign liability management strategy to smooth debt repayments and the development of a domestic FX hedging market to help businesses manage volatility.
 5. To accelerate financial inclusion, NBE should establish a clear and proportionate regulatory framework for digital finance and fintech, drawing lessons from Kenya's regulatory sandbox and Nigeria's payment system oversight. Introducing tiered licensing, risk-based consumer protection, and interoperability standards can promote innovation while managing operational and cyber risks. Finally, accelerating financial inclusion and digital finance demands an enabling rather than restrictive regulatory stance. The NBE should formalize a proportional licensing regime for fintechs and payment service providers, supported by a regulatory sandbox to foster innovation in a controlled environment. Launching a national interoperable digital payment switch is crucial to connect banks, mobile money operators, and fintechs. Consumer protection must be fortified by establishing a dedicated department within the NBE to handle grievances and enforce conduct standards, complemented by a national financial literacy campaign focused on digital finance safety. Integrating the national digital ID with KYC processes will be a key enabler for low-cost, remote account opening.
- Cross-cutting priorities for successful implementation include amending the foundational NBE and banking proclamations to provide a modern legal basis for these reforms, establishing a Centre for Excellence for continuous staff capacity building, and enhancing regional

coordination to harmonize standards. By pursuing this integrated, phased strategy, the NBE can evolve into a modern, stability-focused, and market-enabling regulator capable of supporting Ethiopia's sustainable and inclusive economic growth.

Bibliography

- (IMF), I. M. (2023). Ethiopia: 2023 Article IV Consultation—Staff Report. Washington, DC: IMF.
- Abebe, G. (2020). Bank Supervision in Ethiopia: Capacity Constraints and Risk Management. Ethiopian Journal of Economics.
- Adeosun, T. (2021). Banking sector reforms and prudential regulation in Nigeria. Lagos. CBN Research Department.
- Adrian, T. &. (2010). Liquidity and leverage. . Journal of Financial Intermediation.
- Angelini, P. N. (2014). Monetary and macroprudential policies. . Journal of Money, Credit and Banking.
- Asfaw, M. (2014). Financial Regulation and Supervision in Ethiopia . Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development .
- Beck, T. F. (2011). Making finance work for Africa: Financial sector reforms and financial inclusion. World Bank Policy Paper.
- Bekele, L. (2020). Comparative analysis of banking regulations in East Africa: Where does Ethiopia stand? East African Business Review.
- Board of governance of federal reserve system . (2022). Annual report. Board of governance of federal reserve system .
- Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve. . (2023). Supervision and regulation report. Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve. .
- CBN. . (2022). Regulatory and supervisory framework for Nigerian banks. . Central Bank of Nigeria.
- Central Bank of Kenya (CBK). . (2022). Annual report and financial statements 2021/22. . Nairobi: Central Bank of Kenya.
- Central Bank of Kenya (CBK). (2021). Annual report 2020/2021. Central Bank of Kenya. Central Bank of Kenya (CBK).
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2023). Annual report. CBN.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2022). Annual report and statement of accounts 2022. . Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). .
- Claessens, S. &. (2022). The regulatory responses to the global financial crisis: Some uncomfortable questions. . IMF.
- Claessens, S. G. (2013). Macro-prudential policies to mitigate financial system vulnerabilities. . Journal of International Money and Finance.
- Dr. Suka L. C Adamgbo, C. N. (2024). The Influence of Monetary Policy on Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Nigeria: Monetarist Ideology; Focus on Instruments Directly Under CBN Control. International Research Journal of Economics and Management.
- ECB. (2023). The European Central Bank: History, role and functions 3rd edition. European Central Bank.
- ECB. . (2021). Banking supervision annual report. . European Central Bank.
- European Central Bank (ECB). . (2021). Financial stability review – May 2021. European Central Bank. European Central Bank (ECB). .
- Fantu, B. &. (2022). Financial Regulation in the Horn of Africa: Comparative Analysis of Ethiopia, Kenya, and Rwanda. . East African Journal of Social and Applied Sciences.
- Federal Reserve. (2022). Supervision and regulation report 2022. Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System. Federal Reserve.
- Federal Reserve. (2022). Supervisory and regulatory framework for banking organizations. . Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System.
- Gebremariam, D. &. (2020). An assessment of banking regulations and operational performance: Evidence from Ethiopian commercial banks. Ethiopian Journal of Economics,.
- Geda, A. &. (2020). Monetary Policy and Central Bank Autonomy in Ethiopia: A Political Economy Perspective. . International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability.
- Goldstein, I. &. (2013). Should banks' stress tests be disclosed? Harvard Business School Working Paper.
- Hailu, S. (2021). Fintech Regulation in Emerging Markets: The Case of Ethiopia. African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development.
- Hirtle, B., Kovner, A., & Plosser, M. (2019). The Impact of Supervision on Bank Performance. . Federal Reserve Bank of New York Staff Reports,.
- Ibrahim Alley, H. H. (2023). Banking sector reforms in Nigeria: an empirical appraisal. Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance.
- International Monetary Fund. (2019). IMF Annual Report 2019: Promoting global monetary cooperation and financial stability. IMF.
- Laeven, L., & Valencia, F. (2019). Systemic banking crises database II. IMF Economic Review,.
- Mester, L. J. (2018). Bank supervision, regulation, and risk management: Lessons from theory and practice. Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia.

- Muthiora, B. (2020). Enabling Mobile Money Policies in Kenya: Fostering a Digital Revolution for Financial Inclusion. . GSMA.
- Mwangi, S. &. (2021). The moderating effect of bank size on the relationship between risk appetite and bank performance in Kenya. . Economic Cooperation and Development,.
- National Bank of Ethiopia. (2024). Financial Stability Report 2023. Financial Stability Report 2023. National Bank of Ethiopia.
- Ngugi, R. W. (2019). Financial sector reforms and interest rate liberalization: The Kenya experience. African Economic Research Consortium.
- Nigeria, C. B. (2024). Annual Report. Central Bank of Nigeria.
- Osei-Assibey, E. (2015). Compliance costs and regulatory burden in Ghana's banking sector. . Ghana Journal of Economics,.
- Report., I. M. (2023). The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia: 2023 Article IV Consultation. IMF.
- Reserve Bank of India (RBI). (2020). Report on trend and progress of banking in India 2019–20. . Reserve Bank of India (RBI).
- Sanusi, S. L. (2022). Banking Reform and its Impact on the Nigerian Economy. CBN Journal of Applied Statistics.
- Schoenmaker, D. (2023). The Banking Union: The European Central Bank as a Prudential Supervisor. Oxford University Press.
- Singh, D. &. (2022). The Cambridge Handbook of Twin Peaks Financial Regulation. Cambridge University Press.
- Supervision, Basel Committee on Banking. (2022). Guidelines Corporate governance principles for banks. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision.
- Tadesse, M. &. (2023). Foreign Exchange Regulation and Parallel Market Dynamics in Ethiopia. . World Development.
- Tesfaye, A. (2022). Digital banking and regulatory gaps in Ethiopia: A critical analysis. Ethiopian Journal of Technology and Innovation,.
- Tyce, M. (2020). The Politics of Central Banking in Kenya: Balancing Political and Developmental Interests.
- Tyce, M. (2022). The Politics of Central Banking in Kenya: Balancing Political and Developmental Interests. The University of Manchester.
- Uchenna, E. &. (2019). Regulatory overlap and compliance burden in Nigeria's banking industry. . Nigerian Journal of Finance and Economic Review,.
- Vermeulen, R. H. (2020). The Resilience of Banks in the Euro Area: Stress Test Results and Macroprudential Implications. . ECB .
- Wambui, C. &. (2017). Regulatory compliance and performance of commercial banks in Kenya. . International Journal of Finance and Accounting,.
- WILLINGTON KHALUMI CHIBOLE, D. N. (2022). THE MODERATING EFFECT OF BANK SIZE ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FINANCIAL DISTRESS FACTORS AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN KENYA. the strategic journal of business and change management.
- Wolde, S. (2018). Regulatory frameworks and risk management practices in Ethiopian private banks. International Journal of Banking and Finance,.
- World Bank. . (2020). Financial sector assessment for Ethiopia. Washington, DC: World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2020). Global Financial Development Report 2019/2020: Bank regulation and supervision a decade after the global financial crisis. . World Bank.